

electrochemical deionization technique for preparation of water of conductivity water grade from ordinary tap water.

Experimental

A cell (vide Fig. 1) essentially of the W-tube type with large intermediate zone of 750 ml capacity is charged with ordinary tap water. Few ml of $\sim 10N$ H_2SO_4 and $\sim 10N$ $NaOH$ are added to the anode and cathode solutions respectively. The whole system is then electrolyzed using inert electrodes e.g., platinum, graphite etc. at 60 mA from a regulated D.C. power supply. About 100 volts are necessary to start with. The above cell design has the advantage in preventing the intermixing of solutions of its different compartments through diffusion and convection during electrolysis. A judicious choice of the experimental variables is essential to avoid

FIG. 1.

development of glow-electrolysis phenomenon⁴. The above electrolysis is allowed to continue for 48 hrs or so when the ammeter reading would fall to a figure around 1 mA. The clear liquid so formed in the central conical chamber is of specific conductivity 2×10^{-5} Siemens cm^{-1} at 20° (cf. specific conductivity of original tap water 5×10^{-3} Siemens cm^{-1} at 20°). In the next phase, this liquid in the central chamber is drawn off and transferred to another identical cell where it is electrolyzed without addition of acid and alkali at 300 volts for 24 hr or so at an average current of about 0.3 mA. The water so formed in the central chamber is taken out and collected. It has been found that by this process, water of specific conductivity 4×10^{-6} Siemens cm^{-1} (at 20°) as against the specific conductivity of double distilled water 6×10^{-6} Siemens cm^{-1} (at 20°) can be prepared. It is also of interest to note that total energy to be used for deionization of water by this new technique is about 0.9 times that for preparation of the same quantity of double distilled water by conventional technique. Here the typical results of preliminary experiments have been presented. Further work is

under progress to scale up the process for continuous preparation of much larger quantity of high grade deionized water.

Discussion

The deionization process described is based on the W-tube electrolysis technique introduced by Palit¹ and later theorised and further developed by Sengupta and Palit². During electrolysis of salt solutions in a W-tube, cathode and anode chambers get gradually enriched in alkali and acid respectively, upto the point where the boundaries finally develop. In course of such accumulation when the protons in the anodic section and hydroxyl ions in the cathodic section attain sufficient charge transport capacity, they migrate across the intermediate section in considerable proportion displacing out the ions of the electrolyte to the electrodic sections and finally form water there. It appears that the ions of electrolyte are as if being swept out of this intermediate region by the ions of the solvent. As expected the process has been found to be much accelerated, if at the start of the electrolysis the cathodic and anodic sections be made sufficiently enriched with high concentration of alkali and acid respectively.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. Santi R. Palit for helpful suggestion and discussion.

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Action of some amines as corrosion inhibitor towards corrosion of 63/37 brass in potassium persulphate solutions

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Manuscript received 27 January 1976; revised 11 May 1976; accepted 24 August 1976

POTASSIUM persulphate is a highly corrosive agent for metals and alloys; the rate of dissolution being of the order of 72 $g/m^2/day$.¹ Patel *et al.*²⁻⁵ also studied the corrosion of various types of brass and its inhibition in 0.2M $K_2S_2O_8$ solution. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the effect of some amines on the corrosion of 63/37 brass in 0.1M $K_2S_2O_8$ solution.

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NOTES

Experimental

Brass sheets (63/37), cold rolled and annealed at 550° with the following composition :

Cu—63.2, Zn—36.6, Sn—0.07 and Pb—0.01% were used. Preparation, testing and cleaning procedures for specimens were adopted as described by Champion⁶. In weight loss experiments specimens of size 3×6 cms were fully immersed in beakers

containing 250 ml of 0.1N K₂S₂O₈ solution with and without inhibitors. The reproducibility of the results was ±2%. Results are given in Table 1.

For the galvanostatic studies, the procedure adopted was the same as described by Gatos⁷. The coupons used had an effective area of 2×2 cm², the length of the handle being 4 cm. The current was supplied by storage battery. Results of anode and cathode polarization are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 1—INHIBITION OF CORROSION OF 63/37 BRASS IN 0.1M POTASSIUM PERSULPHATE SOLUTIONS

Size of specimen : 3×6 cm.

Temperature : 30°±1°

Concentration of inhibitor (Molar)	60 minutes		120 minutes		Concentration of inhibitor (Molar)	60 minutes		120 minutes	
	Loss mg	Inhibition %	Loss mg	Inhibition %		Loss mg	Inhibition %	Loss mg	Inhibition %
0.0	250	—	450	—	0.0	250	—	450	—
	<i>α-Picoline</i>					<i>Quinoline</i>			
2.02×10 ⁻²	240	4	440	22	1.69×10 ⁻²	230	8	370	18
4.05×10 ⁻²	180	28	300	33	3.37×10 ⁻²	205	18	350	22
8.09×10 ⁻²	17.0	93	40	91	6.75×10 ⁻²	198	21	316	30
2.02×10 ⁻¹	11.0	96	35	92	1.69×10 ⁻¹	160	36	290	36
	<i>Piperidine</i>					<i>Morpholine</i>			
2.02×10 ⁻²	8.0	97	<0.4	99	2.30×10 ⁻²	80.0	67	90.0	80
4.05×10 ⁻²	<0.3	99	<0.3	99	4.59×10 ⁻²	9.6	97	22.0	92
8.09×10 ⁻²	<0.2	99	<0.3	99	9.18×10 ⁻²	0.7	99	5.0	98
2.02×10 ⁻¹	<0.2	99	<0.8	99	2.30×10 ⁻¹	0.2	99	0.4	99

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CURRENT DENSITY ON ANODE AND CATHODE POLARIZATION

Current density (Amp/cm ²) 10 ⁻³	0.1M K ₂ S ₂ O ₈		0.1M K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ + 2.02×10 ⁻¹ M α-picoline		0.1M K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ + 1.69×10 ⁻¹ M Quinoline		0.1M K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ + 2.02×10 ⁻¹ M Piperidine		0.1M K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ + 2.30×10 ⁻¹ M Morpholine	
	C (mv)	A (mv)	C (mv)	A (mv)	C (mv)	A (mv)	C (mv)	A (mv)	C (mv)	A (mv)
0.0	— 5	— 5	— 50	—50	— 16	—16	+ 40	+40	— 7	— 7
2.0	— 7	+10	— 95	—22	— 36	+25	— 100	+50	— 80	+40
3.0	— 10	+14	—1020	— 9	— 40	+30	— 160	+54	— 300	+45
4.0	— 48	+16	—1100	+20	—170	+36	— 200	+58	— 460	+45
5.0	— 125	+18	—1110	+25	—250	+42	— 310	+60	—1000	+46
7.5	— 660	+18	—1140	+45	—780	+50	—1200	+62	—1180	+48
10.0	— 930	+20	—1160	+60	—800	+56	—1360	+64	—1200	+48
15.0	—1050	+28	—1200	+70	—860	+66	—1400	+72	—1220	+52
25.0	—1200	+36	—1260	+95	—920	+72	—1480	+85	—1260	+60

C = Cathode

A = Anode

Results and Discussion

Morpholine: Morpholine acted as an excellent corrosion inhibitor for brass particularly at a concentration of $2.3 \times 10^{-1} M$. Its inhibitive power increased with increase in its concentrations. Inhibition was practically independent of the duration of the exposure. The galvanostatic measurements showed that in the case of morpholine, the cathodic polarization was remarkable, the anodic polarization being negligible. There was a sudden jump in cathodic polarization between the current density values 4.0 to 5.0×10^{-3} amp/cm². The inhibition is predominantly under cathodic control.

Piperidine: Piperidine gave an excellent inhibition at its lowest concentration i.e., $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$. Its efficiency was found to be independent of its concentration as well as the duration of the exposure. The galvanostatic measurements showed that cathodic polarization was more significant than the anode polarization. At current density value between 5.0×10^{-3} to 7.5×10^{-3} amp/cm², there was a sudden jump in cathodic polarization. The trend in the polarization suggests that the inhibition is under cathodic control.

Quinoline: Quinoline is acted as a poor corrosion inhibitor for 63/37 brass in $0.1 M K_2S_2O_8$ solution. It afforded only 36% protection at its highest concentration i.e., $1.69 \times 10^{-1} M$. Its inhibitive power increases with increase in its concentration. The galvanostatic measurements showed that in the presence of quinoline, both the electrodes were polarized. A sudden increase in the cathodic potential above a current density value of 2.0×10^{-3} amp/cm² indicates film formation over the metal surface.

α -Picoline: It afforded 96% protection at its highest concentration, $2.02 \times 10^{-1} M$. Its inhibitive power remarkably increased with increase in its concentrations; but slightly decreased at the duration of 120 min. From the polarization measurements it is clear that α -picoline acted as a cathodic inhibitor.

The relative order of inhibitive efficiency is :

Piperidine > morpholine > α -picoline > quinoline

Morpholine and piperidine are saturated heterocyclic compounds. Piperidine is a better inhibitor than morpholine. This may be partly due to high electron density over the nitrogen in piperidine (pka = 11.22) than that in morpholine (pka = 8.7).

Quinoline gives quite poor inhibition compared to α -picoline, morpholine and piperidine.

The polarization data reveal that the anode is rarely significantly polarized. Cathode polarization is quite predominant. At higher current densities, in most of the cases, a sudden jump in the cathode polarization is observed indicating formation of a film. This suggests that the inhibition by amines is principally under the cathodic control.

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Studies on Sulphonamides. Part II: Preparation of Ethyl-4-(2-arylsulphonamido-4-phenylsulphonyl-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoate.

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Manuscript received 28 January 1976; revised 3 June 1976; accepted 23 July 1976

THE wide range of chemotherapeutic as well as pharmacodynamic properties of sulphonamides¹⁻⁶, Ethyl-4-aminobenzoate⁷, and *s*-Triazinyl derivatives⁹⁻¹¹ have prompted us to prepare Ethyl-4-(2-arylsulphonamido-4-phenylsulphonyl-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoate with different aryl substitutions as recorded in Table I

2,4-Dichloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl phenyl sulphide (I; $R_1 = R_2 = Cl$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$), prepared from the reaction of cyanuric chloride (I; $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = Cl$) with thiophenol¹² at 0° , was made to react with ethyl-4-aminobenzoate at 30° - 35° to afford compound (I; $R_1 = Cl$, $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC Ph. NH-$, $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$ which on subsequent treatment with excess ammonia in dioxan medium furnished the corresponding 2-amino compound. The product thus obtained was refluxed with different arylsulphonyl chloride to give the corresponding sulphonamides which were finally oxidised to respective sulphones.

Experimental

(a) 2,4-Dichloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl phenyl sulphide (I; $R_1 = R_2 = Cl$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$):

To cyanuric chloride (I; $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = Cl$) (18.45 g.) in acetone (30 ml) kept at 0° , a solution of thiophenol (11 g.) in acetone (15 ml.) was gradually added with constant stirring followed by addition of aqueous sodium hydroxide (100 ml. 4%). The reaction mixture was stirred for half an hour and poured in crushed ice. The product obtained was